

Muography on Dry Stored Spent Nuclear Fuel

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Abstract—Operating nuclear power plants poses the challenge of effectively handling spent nuclear fuel, the byproduct of the energy generation process. As part of the waste management strategy, various countries store the spent fuel in dedicated casks specially designed to effectively shield the radiation from humans and the environment. Traditional monitoring methods for these casks face limitations in resolving the cask’s inventory to a small scale. In response, muography, an innovative imaging technique utilizing cosmic muons, is being researched. It measures and analyzes the changes in the flux of cosmic muons before and after traversing the spent fuel cask. The cosmic particles possess the potential to enhance resolution at smaller scales. This technique can offer valuable insights into its content and eventually the integrity of spent fuel assemblies and spent fuel rods. This paper provides an overview of the application, limitations, and potential of muography for spent fuel storage casks, with a particular focus on the CASTOR® V/19 cask.

Index Terms—Cosmic Muons, Spent Fuel, Dual Purpose Casks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Muon radiography or tomography, jointly known as muography, is a rising cutting-edge imaging method for visualizing large, dense geometries. The technique uses cosmic particles generated by the interaction of cosmic rays with the Earth’s atmosphere. By analyzing the absorption and/or the scattering of the particles, information about internal structures is gained [1], [2]. Muons were discovered in 1936 by Carl D. Anderson and Seth Neddermeyer [3]. They possess the remarkable ability to penetrate dense and thick materials, making them exceptionally suitable for imaging hidden structures. The first notable application of cosmic muography was conducted by Luis Alvarez in the 1960s. Alvarez and his team utilized muon detection to search for hidden chambers within the Pyramid of Khafre in Egypt. Although no unknown chambers were identified, this marked one of the initial milestones in applied muography [4].

Beyond archaeological applications [5], muography has been adapted for various practical uses. It has been employed in volcanology to study volcano structures or in border control and security. In the nuclear sector, it is used to monitor and inspect reactor cores. A particularly groundbreaking application within the nuclear sector is the visualization of the interior of spent fuel casks where traditional inspection methods often face challenges with limited penetration depth and resolution. Muography offers a promising alternative with its ability to provide non-destructive, highly penetrating, and accurate imaging. It aims specifically to enhance our ability to reveal the distribution of spent fuel within casks and identify potential structural anomalies. Moreover, it seeks to assess cask integrity without requiring direct access, thereby significantly improving efficiency of spent fuel management and enhance the understanding of long-term fuel rod behavior.

This paper specifically investigates the application and its progress of muography for monitoring spent nuclear fuel casks using the example of a CASTOR® V/19 cask. It aims to provide a compact overview of its motivation, techniques and challenges in the nuclear waste management sector. This study highlights new possibilities for enhancing our understanding of stored nuclear fuel and its behavior during interim storage.

II. COSMIC MUONS

Cosmic muons are elementary particles belonging to the lepton family and are produced in the upper atmosphere (approximately 15km) through cosmic ray collisions with atmospheric nuclei. These collisions create a cascade of secondary particles, including charged mesons that decay into muons. The primary decay channels are charged pions and kaons. Kaons either decay into muons or into pions, which then decay into muons (compare Fig. 1) [6].

Fig. 1. Illustration depicting cosmic rays interacting with the atmosphere and generating secondary particles, such as muons. Source: [7]

Cosmic muons possess remarkable penetrating power and exhibit relativistic velocities. Their high velocities allow them to reach the Earth’s surface before decaying despite their mean lifetime of approximately $2.2 \mu\text{s}$. This makes them the most abundant charged particles at sea level. At this altitude, muons have a mean energy of approximately 4 GeV. Their angular distribution as a function of the zenith angle θ follows $\cos^2 \theta$. The interaction of muons with matter is primarily determined by the weak nuclear force and the electromagnetic interaction, allowing them to penetrate large thicknesses of material [6].

Muography exploits multiple Coloumb scattering of cosmic ray muons, causing deviations in the particle path. The scattering distribution can be described using a Gaussian approximation with a root mean square width of

$$\theta_0 = \frac{13.6 \text{ MeV}}{\beta c p} z \sqrt{\frac{L}{L_0}} \left[1 + 0.038 \ln \left(\frac{L z^2}{L_0 \beta^2} \right) \right], \quad (1)$$

where p , βc and z represent the incident particles momentum (in $[\text{MeV}c^{-1}]$), the velocity and the charge number. L/L_0 is the thickness of the scattering medium in radiation lengths [6], [8].

Cosmic muons are already used for imaging in various research fields. Using the principles of muography detailed information about the density distribution and composition of materials traversed by cosmic muons can be obtained. Their interactions are more pronounced in denser materials and in those with higher atomic numbers [8], [9]. The analysis of muon flux, stopping powers and angular distribution before and after passing through an object allows for insights into their interactions with matter. Using reconstruction algorithms, high-resolution three-dimensional images of the object can be generated [1], [10]. This capability provides detailed information about internal structures, even in cases where traditional imaging methods face limitations. Such advanced imaging techniques are particularly valuable in the study of spent nuclear fuel.

III. SPENT NUCLEAR FUEL

Globally, nuclear power plants are producing a significant amount of spent nuclear fuel produced after uranium fuel is utilized to generate electricity. The fuel cycle starts with uranium mining and processing into uranium oxide concentrate, known as "yellowcake." This yellowcake is enriched to increase the concentration of the ^{235}U , which is essential for sustaining nuclear reactions. The enriched uranium is fabricated into ceramic pellets, which are loaded into tubes called fuel rods. These rods are assembled into fuel assemblies and loaded into the reactor core. Depending on the reactor type, a specific number of these assemblies are used to operate it. An exemplary 15x15-16 fuel assembly used in the most common reactor type, the Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR), is depicted in Fig. 2. A fuel assembly also includes guide tubes and an instrument tube, neither of which contains fuel pellets. In the reactor, ^{235}U undergoes fission, releasing a significant amount of energy. Over time, the concentration of fissionable material decreases, and the fuel becomes less efficient, eventually being replaced by fresh fuel. The spent fuel is then removed from the reactor. Spent nuclear fuel consists of a high percentage of ^{238}U , with a small remaining amount of ^{235}U , fission products, and transuranic elements such as plutonium, neptunium, americium, and curium. These components are highly radioactive and generate heat, necessitating careful handling and storage. Therefore, immediately after removal from the reactor, spent fuel is stored in water-filled pools adjacent to the reactor. The water cools the fuel and provides radiation shielding. After a dedicated time, the spent fuel can be transferred to dry storage casks. Information taken from [12].

Fig. 2. Illustrated is an example of a fuel assembly with one instrument tube, 16 guide tubes and 208 fuel rods. In addition, spacer grids are shown, which hold the fuel rods in place using springs. Head and bottom nozzles are not visible. The cladding, guide and instrument tubes, as well as the fuel pellets are shown in more detail on the right. Together they build a 15x15-16 fuel assembly. Source: [11]

IV. SPENT FUEL CASK - THE CASTOR[®] V/19

Spent nuclear fuel is usually characterized as high-level radioactive waste. Although it accounts for only 3% of all nuclear waste, it contains 95% of its radioactivity, which requires careful handling and disposal to avoid harm to the environment and humans [13]. Depending on the country and the reactor type, spent fuel is stored and transported in designated storage casks, like the cask series CASTOR[®] [14]. They are utilized for transportation and storage of spent nuclear fuel from research reactors, vitrified reprocessing and from Boiling Water Reactors (BWR) and PWR's. The casks are designed to effectively and safely shield the radiation emitted by the radioactive inventory. Among these casks is the CASTOR[®] V/19 [15], specially designed for a maximum number of 19 fuel assemblies from PWR's (see Fig. 3). With an overall height of 594 cm and an outer diameter of 244 cm, the CASTOR[®] V/19 has an empty weight of approx. 108 tons. Its monolithic ductile cast iron body, with axial boreholes filled with polyethylene moderator rods, guarantees efficient neutron moderation. The fuel basket, situated within the cask, securely holds the fuel assemblies. The safe containment of radioactive materials is ensured by lids and additional polyethylene moderators. The two barriers of the lid system are permanently being monitored for leak tightness. This is performed by a pressure switch integrated into the secondary lid. This robust construction not only ensures the safe containment of radioactive materials but also mitigates radiation exposure risks to personnel and the environment [14]. The self-shielding environment of spent fuel casks poses challenges for conventional non-destructive visualization methods, limiting their effectiveness. Loaded CASTOR[®] V/19 casks comprise a variety of materials such as polyethylene, cast iron, stainless steel, zirconium alloys, and uranium oxide, consequently exhibit a range of densities and atomic numbers. This diversity of materials motivates the investigation of the usage of cosmic muon tomography on loaded storage casks.

Fig. 3. CASTOR® V/19 cask labeled with main individual geometries. Source: [14].

V. MOTIVATION BEHIND MUOGRAPHY ON DRY SPENT NUCLEAR FUEL

The majority of countries operating nuclear power plants are still searching for a comprehensive and definitive solution for managing high-level radioactive waste. Currently, spent fuel casks are often either stored on-site or transported to designated above-ground facilities, where they remain until final storage decisions are made [13], [16]. Ensuring the protection of human health and the environment is the top priority in the storage of high-level radioactive materials and is achieved through various safety measures. As the duration of interim storage extends, for example in Germany, where the first spent fuel casks were loaded almost 40 years ago, questions naturally arise about the changes in the fuel rods over time [17]. Therefore, research is essential to prove the continued safety and integrity of stored fuel assemblies. This research requires a thorough understanding of the long-term effects of various factors on the internal conditions of the stored fuel assemblies.

Developing reliable and validated theoretical methods for predicting and simulating the behavior of fuel rods is crucial [17]. These methods are essential for assessing the impact of individual effects on the integrity of cladding tubes and the fuel itself. Additional experimental data on the interior conditions can be beneficial for a comprehensive study. It is of significant scientific interest to understand the long-term development and changes within the casks. Reliable estimates for the visualisation of individual fuel rods or density changes in certain areas can represent significant progress in the research

of extended interim storage. As classical non-invasive imaging methods, such as temperature, neutron, and gamma-ray measurements, are not sufficient for high-resolution imaging of individual geometries, muography offers a promising way to address those limitations. By utilizing cosmic-ray muons to image the internal structure of spent fuel casks, it can help to understand the condition and integrity of the interior over extended periods. This capability is particularly valuable in assessing potential structural degradation or anomalies that may arise due to aging infrastructure.

In addition physical investigations of cask interiors are invasive, costly, time-consuming, or not feasible. The latter is mainly due to the unavailability of sufficiently large hot cells. Using cosmic muons can address these limitations effectively. Another potential application could facilitate the evaluation of the positioning and integrity of fuel rods after the transfer of casks from interim storage to final repositories. By visualising the three-dimensional density distribution of fuel rods, muography could identify individual rods and detect potential fuel leakage within the cask. In this way, handling procedures can be optimised and potential radiation exposure during potential fuel transfer can be reduced.

Overall, muography possesses the capability to improve the efficiency of spent fuel management by providing detailed insight into the condition of spent fuel, addressing potential future regulatory requirements and enhancing the scientific understanding of nuclear waste management. The ability to comprehensively monitor throughout the life cycle of spent fuel supports overall management, making it a pioneering tool for ensuring the continued safe and efficient storage of spent fuel.

VI. CHALLENGES OF MUOGRAPHY

Muography offers considerable promise for imaging spent fuel casks, though it does encounter challenges. One notable aspect is the complex and dense shielding of the casks, designed to contain radiation, which can attenuate muons and affect image resolution. Although high-density materials and multiple scattering events within the cask can complicate data interpretation, ongoing improvements in analysis algorithms are improving the accuracy of image reconstruction. Furthermore, while its spatial resolution is currently lower [18] than some conventional radiographic techniques, its capacity to visualize internal structures deeply and non-destructively makes it a powerful tool for investigating spent fuel casks. Advances in muon detection and imaging technology are expected to continue enhancing the effectiveness of muography, further strengthening its role in safety assessments and long-term integrity evaluations.

Installing muography systems in an interim storage facility presents unique logistical opportunities and challenges. While factors such as restricted access to certain areas, strict safety protocols, and the need to maintain uninterrupted storage operations can influence implementation, these challenges also drive innovation in system design and deployment strategies. Addressing these operational constraints can lead to more efficient integration of muography into existing workflows,

ultimately enhancing its effectiveness and applicability in monitoring and evaluating spent fuel storage conditions [18].

While ongoing advancements in muon detectors, data processing algorithms, and simulation techniques are essential for further improving imaging resolution and reliability in dense and shielded environments, muography already stands out as a valuable tool. It can significantly enhance our understanding of spent fuel storage conditions and plays a crucial role in supporting safety assessments in nuclear facilities.

VII. MUOGRAPHY ON SPENT FUEL STORAGE CASKS

Muography relies on the principle of measuring the flux of cosmic muons before and after they traverse an object. By surrounding a spent fuel cask, e.g. a CASTOR[®] V/19 cask, the incoming and outgoing flux of muons can be captured. As muons interact more frequently with materials of higher density or atomic number, the flux of muons is influenced by the density distribution within the object being scanned. The materials within CASTOR[®] V/19 casks exhibit a wide range of densities, with the density and atomic number of the spent nuclear fuel significantly differing from the surrounding materials. As a result, the muons experience a greater deflection in the region of the fuel rods due to their interaction with the higher density material. This interaction results in noticeable differences in the flux measured after passing through the spent nuclear fuel. The detectors capture various parameters, such as absorption rate, stopping power, and muon deflection. These parameters are then processed by analysis algorithms to reconstruct the internal structure of the scanned object.

Both theoretical and experimental research is advancing the feasibility of muography applications, particularly in the sector of safeguards. In 2023, the first measurement campaign within an interim storage facility in Germany was conducted. The campaign involved two CASTOR[®] V/19 casks: one containing solely spent fuel assemblies and one with a mixed configuration of spent fuel assemblies and three centrally positioned dummy elements. One dummy element was located at the center of the fuel basket, with the other two symmetrically placed to its left and right. The aim of the campaign was to both use muon absorption rates and scattering angles to distinguish between dummy elements and spent fuel assemblies. However, the analysis so far has focused only on absorption data. For the measurement campaign drift tube detectors with a spatial resolution of approximately 350 μm were employed. The detectors, equipped with 4.5-meter-tall drift tubes, were designed to cover the full length and width of the fuel basket. For alignment, an additional, smaller detector was at a fixed position on top of the cask. Each cask was measured from three distinct detector positions. In total, the cask containing the dummy elements was measured for 18 days, while the cask with solely fuel assemblies was measured for 11 days. Initial data analysis indicates that muography was successful in resolving two out of the three dummy elements in the spent nuclear fuel cask [18], [19]. An image of the experimental setup, taken in the reception area of the interim storage facility in Grafenrheinfeld, Germany, is shown in Fig. 4. In the setup, two drift tube detectors are positioned opposite each other to capture muons penetrating the cask.

Fig. 4. A CASTOR[®] V/19 cask surrounded by two drift tube detectors to capture the cosmic muon flux. Source: [18], [19]

Prior to that, Los Alamos National Laboratories (LANL) conducted measurements on a partially loaded Westinghouse MC-10 fuel cask. The cask was partially loaded with 18 out of 24 fuel assemblies. The missing fuel assemblies were grouped near the cask body. The detectors used in this campaign were based on the drift tube technology, with two muon trackers positioned around the cask, one elevated by 1.2 m relative to the other. Since the detectors cover less than half of the cask's diameter at a time, nine measurement positions were required to cover the entire area of interest. A rough pre-alignment of the detectors was performed manually during the measurement, followed by fine alignment using commonly known techniques to align charged particle tracking detectors. Each position was measured for a period of 10 days resulting in a total measurement time of approximately 90 days. The analysis relied on scattering angles to detect and characterize missing spent fuel assemblies. The results demonstrated the ability to effectively identify and characterize the missing assemblies [20]. Both the measurement campaign in Grafenrheinfeld, Germany, and the one at LANL faced challenges related to background noise. In both cases triggers were used to reduce the number of noise hits. As a result, at LANL, the overall tracking efficiency was reduced by approximately 50%. Although this resulted in a loss of efficiency, these results further support the potential of muography in accurately assessing the condition and configuration of fuel assemblies within storage casks.

To increase the potential of muography for managing spent

fuel casks beyond its applications in safeguards, significant improvements towards single rod resolution are required. The current focus of theoretical studies aims to enhance the resolution to a level where individual fuel rods, rather than just assemblies, can be accurately visualized. This necessitates advanced simulations using tools such as the Monte Carlo-based simulation toolkit Geant4 [21], [22], which can accurately mimic the passage of particles through a spent fuel cask. The resulting data on scattering and absorption are crucial to understand muon behavior within large structures like the CASTOR® V/19 cask. Furthermore, a sufficiently detailed model of a cask is essential, as inaccuracies in this model can lead to deviations in the scattering and absorption data, significantly influencing the analysis [23]. Creating a well-designed simulation setup enables researchers to study the theoretical behavior of muons and determine their interaction locations, facilitating a comprehensive analysis.

In [24], it was demonstrated that, under suitable conditions, missing fuel rods can be identified. In this study, detectors were positioned above and below an upright cask model, which was represented as two rectangular planes with vanishing thickness. Three fuel rods were removed from the central fuel assembly. By simulating the overall cask model while focusing on the inner assembly, it was found that, e.g., for simulations with 10^8 mono-directional ($\theta_{in} = 0$) muons, all three fuel rods could be identified as missing. Although achieving the resolution necessary to experimentally identify individual fuel rods within a cask is not yet feasible, these findings represent a promising step forward.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The overview highlights the potential of muography as a method for inspecting spent fuel storage casks, particularly focusing on the CASTOR® V/19 cask. Its ability to provide detailed imaging without physical access offers significant advantages in assessing the integrity of fuel rods, potentially important for spent nuclear fuel disposal. Recent experimental campaigns have demonstrated promising results, indicating the feasibility of visualizing fuel assemblies or distinguishing between fuel assemblies and dummy elements within storage casks. While challenges remain, including achieving higher resolutions within feasible time frames, the findings represent a notable advancement in nuclear fuel inspection methodologies. The growing interest and investment in muography underscore its potential as a valuable tool for enhancing nuclear safety and waste management practices globally.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank Maik Stuke for his valuable guidance, encouragement and support during the research project.

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